

BEHAVIOR OF UNIDIRECTIONAL GLASS FIBER REINFORCED EPOXY AT LOW TEMPERATURE UNDER TENSILE IMPACT

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ABSTRACT

The behavior of GFRP at R.T.(room temperature), -50°C , -100°C , and -150°C under tensile impact was studied on the modified bar-to-bar assembly with a self-designed low temperature box. It shows that GFRP is of high strength ductility at low temperature, and the assembly is suitable for such experiment.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the temperature dependent behavior of materials has been paid much attention^{1,2,3}. The temperature dependent constitutive relations of composites has also been one of the topics concerned. The earliest work in this respect was carried out by Kawata in 1982⁴. He used a low temperature box (Fig.1), which is similar to the one used in measuring impact toughness at low temperature, on a self-designed block-to-bar type tensile impact set. As the specimen in the low temperature box reaches the premeditated temperature, the box is moved rapidly and an impact is applied immediately. The stress-strain curve under tensile impact of woven cloth reinforced epoxy at 77K was obtained primarily. However, Kawata didn't carry out the impact test of unidirectional fiber reinforced composites at an arbitrary low temperature, and the testing temperature may be somewhat different from that in the box, furthermore, the temperature distribution in specimen might not be uniform. Nevertheless, his test method is helpful and Kawata is a pioneer in this field. In order to overcome deficiencies mentioned above, a testing set was designed for giving impact directly at various levels of temperature and keeping the temperature in specimen constant and uniform. Hence, more reliable tensile impact behavior of unidirectional glass fiber reinforced epoxy can be studied at different low temperatures.

Fig.1

- 1-low temperature box
- 2-impact block
- 3-specimen
- 4-output bar

EXPERIMENTAL EQUIPMENT

The authors' former works^{5,6} were conducted on a self-designed tensile impact equipment mainly at

R.T. For test at low temperature, the equipment was improved both in loading device and in temperature device.

1. Loading Device

A block-to-bar type of this device was changed to a bar-to-bar type. The new loading device is shown sketchily in Fig.2, and the whole equipment is shown in Fig.3. In Fig.2, if the right surface of block 6 is hit by a pendulum, the short metal bar 2 connected with the block 6

Fig. 2

- | | | | |
|------------|-------------------|--------------|--------|
| 1—brake | 2—short metal bar | 3—input bar | 4—tube |
| 5—specimen | 6—impact block | 7—output bar | |

Fig. 3

- | | | |
|--------------|----------------|-----------------------|
| 1—pendulum | 2—impact block | 3—short metal bar |
| 4—gauge | 5—input bar | 6—low temperature box |
| 7—output bar | 8—tail stock | |

will break and then produces and transmits a rectangular tensile stress wave through the input bar 3. The short metal bar made of aluminium alloy has a property of nearly ideal plasticity. As this stress wave propagates to specimen 5, the specimen will also break due to the tensile impact. Herein a brake 1 is arranged to prevent the input bar 3 from rushing out. Meanwhile, a tube 4 is mounted around the specimen, so that not only the fracture of broken specimen is enclosed but also the temperature difference of joining parts between the threaded ends of specimen and input bar or output bar may be eliminated properly. (The form of specimen is shown in Fig.4, and its processing refers to ref.7.) As seen in Fig.3, owing to the use of a bar-to-bar type, the box 6 can be placed keeping the specimen at a constant low temperature, and this temperature may be measured precisely. The uniformity of temperature in specimen is guaranteed.

Fig.4

2. Low Temperature Device

The self-designed low temperature device is made up of two halves, the upper one can be removed for the convenience of installing specimen. (Fig.5) The work cavity and liquid nitrogen storage cavity in both halves are cylindrical in order to provide an axial symmetrical temperature field in work cavity. The heat insulator is made of superfine glass wool. After injecting liquid nitrogen into the cavity the natural temperature recovering curve in work cavity is measured as shown in Fig.6. The largest gradient of that curve is $2.3^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$, and during the first 20 minutes the curve is nearly horizontal. For impact test, this time region is sufficient. So the whole testing process may be

Fig. 5

considered isothermal. It is easily seen that the natural temperature recovering curve for different initial $\bar{\gamma}$ temperature may be obtained by changing the injecting amount of liquid nitrogen. The beginning part of these curves is also horizontal, then the test results at different low temperatures can be obtained.

Fig.6

Fig. 7

a—measured curve
b—calculated result
Dotted line is the temperature
in low temperature box

In order to study the temperature effect to stress wave propagation in the input and output bars, both calculation and measurement of temperature distribution in these bars have been carried out. Calculation is based on one dimensional heat conduction theory, and measurement is based on the principle that the electrical resistance of semi-conductor strain gauge changes with the change of temperature. These results are shown in Fig.7, one can see that the temperature gradient is large at a distance less than 200 mm from the end connected with the specimen. According to ref.8, the error

of modulus of these bars owing to the nonuniformity of temperature distribution is within 3%, and in addition, according to Campbell's analysis⁹, the non-uniform effect of strain is within 1%. These errors are acceptable. So that this device is applicable and satisfactory for tensile impact test at low temperature.

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

According to Fig.3, strain gauge are pasted on input and output bars respectively. Just like the measuring technique of Hopkinson pressure bar, X-t diagram of stress wave propagation in input bar, specimen and output bar is shown in Fig.8. In Fig.8, the block diagram of all measuring apparatus is also given. According to ref.5, the strain $\epsilon_s(t)$, strain rate $\dot{\epsilon}_s(t)$, and stress $\sigma_s(t)$ of specimen can be given from the measured strain $\epsilon_i(t)$ and $\epsilon_t(t)$. The former is the signal of incident wave in input bar, and the latter is that of translucent wave in output bar.

Fig.8

Then

$$\epsilon_s(t) = \frac{2C_0}{l_0} \int_0^t [\epsilon_i(\tau) - \epsilon_t(\tau)] d\tau \quad (1)$$

$$\dot{\epsilon}_s(t) = \frac{2C_0}{l_0} [\epsilon_i(t) - \epsilon_t(t)] \quad (2)$$

$$\sigma_s(t) = \frac{EA}{A_s} \epsilon_s(t) \quad (3)$$

where $C_0 = \sqrt{E/\rho}$ is the wave speed in both input and output bars (since they are made of the same material), E and ρ are the modulus and density of both bars, respectively, l_0 is the testing length of specimen, A and A_s are areas of cross section of output bar and specimen, respectively. Fig.9 shows a standardly measured diagram of incident and translucent wave of these bars. Subsequently, after the data processing by a computer one can get the stress-strain curve at a certain average strain rate.

Fig.9

Fig.10

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The specimen is made of prepreg. Its curing process is shown in Fig.10. The results for R.T., $-50^{\circ}C$, $-100^{\circ}C$, and $-150^{\circ}C$ are shown in Table 1 and Fig.11 and 12.

Fig. 11

Fig. 12

Table 1

Temperature $T(^{\circ}C)$	-150	-100	-50	R.T.
Maximum Stress σ_b (Gpa)	1.77	1.62	1.56	1.49
Fracture Strain ϵ_b (%)	10.7	10.4	9.9	11.1
Fracture Work U (Mpa)	135	124	113	115

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

1. It will be seen from the results that the strength of GFRP increases with the drop of temperature. The strength at $-150^{\circ}C$ is about 20% higher than that at R.T., so this composite is temperature dependent, coldshort isn't present and the fracture work increases slightly with the drop of tempera-

ture. Therefore, the composite, 0° -directional glass fiber reinforced epoxy, is of high strength ductility at low temperature.

2. After loading to the maximum value σ_b , the stress in specimen doesn't decrease to zero immediately, but decreases slightly with some shaking. This reflects a cumulative fracture of fibers. Before σ_b , only few fibers are broken, and after σ_b , numerous fibers are broken. This agrees with the results obtained by means of acoustic emission method (AEM). In view of fracture mechanics, the quick expanding of cracks may be interrupted by the anisotropy of this composite, hence, the specimen would not suddenly lose the whole loading capacity.

3. The results show that the temperature-dependence isn't so obvious as the strain rate dependence⁵ of this composite, the dynamic fracture elongation ($\dot{\epsilon} \sim 10^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$) is several times than the static elongation, but the effect of temperature doesn't exceed 20%. Moreover, from the fracture form under impact, the fracture form at both low and room temperature are the same in general. One can infer that the fracture mechanism should be the same also.

4. Fracture work U is counted by the area below the stress-strain curve till σ_b . However, the absorbed energy is larger than U . For impact the area beyond σ_b may be applied to absorb more energy. It might be of advantage for structure design of this composite.

5. The self-designed low temperature device, as well as bar-to-bar type loading device are effective for tensile impact test. The low temperature device is good in its performance, facile to control, and utilizable to tensile impact test under a hygrothermal environment with a little modification. The bar-to-bar type loading device may be used to study the constitutive relation of various loading and unloading, by changing the incident wave through selecting the short metal bar (material and/or size).

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5. Damage

